

Thermodynamically stable greigite (Fe_3S_4) reshapes the Fe–S and Fe–S–O predominance diagrams

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Abstract

Greigite (Fe_3S_4), an iron thiospinel and an important ferrimagnetic mineral in sedimentary environments, has long been regarded as metastable. Recent calorimetry indicates that greigite is thermodynamically stable in the Fe–S system, so the classical Fe–S and Fe–S–O predominance diagrams require reassessment. Using a CALPHAD workflow built on pycalphad and a unified thermodynamic database that incorporates the measured greigite data, we recompute these diagrams and compare them with the classical assessments.

Treating greigite as metastable reproduces the classical Fe–S and Fe–S–O topologies, validating the database and method. Introducing stable greigite substantially modifies both systems: in Fe–S, greigite occupies an intermediate position between metallic iron and pyrite, analogous to magnetite in Fe–O, and the equilibrium pyrrhotite field is absent for the mean greigite enthalpy of formation, reappearing only within its experimental uncertainty. In Fe–S–O, greigite borders the iron oxides directly, displacing the classical pyrite–hematite contact. Differential scanning calorimetry and powder X-ray diffraction show that greigite persists to approximately 600 K before transforming to pyrite and pyrrhotite. The results show that closely balanced thermodynamic parameters can yield markedly different yet equally admissible phase diagrams, with implications for low-temperature iron-sulfide equilibria in geochemical systems. All code, databases, and data are openly available.

Keywords: CALPHAD; greigite; Fe–S–O phase diagram; thermodynamics

1. Introduction

Greigite (Fe_3S_4), the iron thiospinel and sulfide analogue of magnetite (Fe_3O_4), has long been considered metastable following the solubility measurements of Berner (1967). Recent calorimetric and thermodynamic studies (Subramani et al., 2020; Shumway et al., 2022) have revised its thermodynamic properties and shown that it is stable in the Fe–S system. The classical Fe–S and Fe–S–O stability (predominance) diagrams (Holland, 1959; Toulmin & Barton, 1964) predate these data and omit greigite from the equilibrium iron-sulfide assemblages, so the Fe–S and Fe–S–O stability relationships warrant re-evaluation. Greigite is also a significant

ferrimagnetic carrier in marine and lacustrine sediments and a sensitive indicator of sedimentary redox conditions in terrestrial and Martian environments, so its equilibrium stability bears directly on the paleomagnetic and diagenetic record (Yu et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2026; Rickard et al., 2024; Li et al., 2014; Hurowitz et al., 2025).

Here we recalculate the Fe–S and Fe–S–O phase stability diagrams using an open-source CALPHAD (CALculation of PHase Diagrams) workflow and a thermodynamic database assembled from the published literature on iron sulfides and oxides. We compare the revised diagrams with the classical assessments, evaluate the effect of the uncertainty in the greigite data, and discuss the implications for low-temperature Fe–S equilibria. A central result, likely relevant to other geochemical systems, is that uncertainties in closely balanced thermodynamic parameters can produce significantly different phase diagrams that are all consistent with the measured thermodynamics.

2. Methods

All databases and predominance diagrams in this work were produced by an open, reproducible workflow built on the CALPHAD library pycalphad. The workflow (Table 1, Fig. S1) retrieves the assessed Fe–S and Ca–Fe–O–S databases from a literature index, ingests the greigite calorimetry as typed, source-linked values (each retaining its primary-source citation), assembles a single Fe–S(–O) database deterministically on a common SGTE91 reference, and computes the predominance diagrams by grand-potential minimization over the redox plane on a grid. Every thermodynamic value is traceable to a primary source and the assembled database is rebuilt deterministically from that record (Section 7).

Table 1 Workflow steps

Step	What it does	Tool	Output (this work)
1. Database lookup	Retrieves the assessed Fe–S and Ca–Fe–O–S databases from the literature index	TDB-DB lookup	Dilner 2015 Fe–S + Dilner 2017 Ca–Fe–O–S (.tdb)
2. Provenance manifest	Reads the greigite enthalpy, entropy and heat capacity as typed, source-linked values from the exported knowledge-graph manifest	provenance_manifest.json (typed KG export)	Subramani 2020; Shumway 2022 → typed measured values
3. TDB stitching	Graft greigite (and pyrite) into one database; dedupe functions; build deterministically	Python stitch script	single Fe–S(–O) .tdb (byte-reproducible)
4. Predominance plotting	Minimize the grand potential over the redox plane to find	pycalphad 0.11.1 optimizer	Fe–S and Fe–S–O predominance

	the stable phase at each point	diagrams
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By mapping redox conditions (T , $f(\text{S}_2)$, $f(\text{O}_2)$) to the stable Fe–S(–O) phase, the diagrams link depositional environment to mineralogy and to the paleomagnetic and redox signals that greigite carries as a ferrimagnetic Fe(II,III) thiospinel.

2.1 Thermodynamic database

Phase equilibria were computed with pycalphad 0.11.1 on a single thermodynamic database. The Fe–S basis is the Dilner–Mao–Selleby (2015) assessment, in which pyrrhotite was modelled as a non-stoichiometric $(\text{Fe}, \text{Va})_1\text{S}_1$ phase (Wang & Salveson, 2005) and used at its energy-minimized composition (troilite-end $\text{FeS}_{1.00}$ – $\text{FeS}_{1.14}$), consistent with troilite as the stable low-temperature monosulfide (Grønvold & Stølen, 1992; Toulmin & Barton, 1964; Nakazawa & Morimoto, 1971). This choice changed the calculated decomposition margin (Section 4.1) by less than $2 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ relative to stoichiometric FeS.

Greigite was added as a stoichiometric Fe_3S_4 line compound built from the measured enthalpy of formation $\Delta_f H^\circ = -144.1 \pm 7.3 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ per $\text{FeS}_{1.33}$ (Subramani et al., 2020) and entropy $S^\circ(298) = 71.334 \text{ J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$. Direct high-temperature heat-capacity measurement is precluded because greigite decomposes to pyrite and pyrrhotite on heating and is highly sensitive to surface oxidation. An upper limit of 600 K was set from the differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements reported here and from prior DSC and in situ powder X-ray diffraction (Chen et al., 2019), which place the onset of transformation near this temperature. Above the measured range (0–300 K) The greigite heat capacity was represented with the Debye–Einstein fit of Shumway et al. (2022) (Fig. S2).

For Fe–S–O we used the Dilner & Selleby (2017) Ca–Fe–O–S assessment, which includes the iron oxides (wüstite, magnetite, hematite), sulfates, native sulfur, and an O_2/S_2 gas; pyrite and the measured greigite were grafted on.

Because this database, the Fe–S assessment, and the greigite description share the same SGTE91 elemental reference (GHSER), all phases are evaluated on a common reference state, so Gibbs-energy differences, reaction energies, and phase equilibria are thermodynamically consistent across the assembled database while preserving the phase relationships of the original assessments. Two minor, logged repairs to the source databases were required (an archive-extractor fix and removal of byte-identical duplicate functions); no thermodynamic values were changed. The consistency is supported by the OECD–NEA (2020) iron assessment and by the validation in Section 3.

2.2 Predominance (phase-stability) diagrams and uncertainty

Following Holland (1959), phase stability was evaluated using the grand potential formalism. At each point of the $\log f(\text{O}_2)$, $\log f(\text{S}_2)$ plane the stable phase is the one that minimizes the grand potential per mole of iron:

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega &= G - \nu_{S_2} \cdot \mu_{S_2} - \nu_{O_2} \cdot \mu_{O_2}, \\ \mu_{S_2} &= G^\circ_{S_2} + RT \log f(S_2) \\ \mu_{O_2} &= G^\circ_{O_2} + RT \log f(O_2)\end{aligned}$$

Here Ω is the grand potential per mole of iron, G the Gibbs energy per mole of iron of the phase, $\nu(S_2)$ and $\nu(O_2)$ the moles of S_2 and O_2 exchanged per mole of iron, and $\mu(S_2)$, $\mu(O_2)$ the chemical potentials of the S_2 and O_2 reservoirs. The fugacity f is the effective (thermodynamic) partial pressure:

$$\mu(X_2) = G^\circ(X_2) + RT \ln f(X_2).$$

The chemical potentials of the S_2 and O_2 reservoirs were obtained from the corresponding gas-species Gibbs energies in the database. Phase boundaries and predominance fields follow directly from the thermodynamic calculation, with no fitted, statistical, or machine-learning models.

The Fe–S–O predominance diagram was calculated up to the sulfur-saturation boundary, corresponding to equilibrium with native orthorhombic sulfur. The sulfur fugacity at this boundary is given by

$$\log f(S_2) = \frac{2 G^\circ(S, \text{orthorhombic}) - G^\circ(S_2, \text{gas})}{RT \ln 10}$$

where $G^\circ(S, \text{orthorhombic})$ and $G^\circ(S_2, \text{gas})$ are the standard-state Gibbs energies of crystalline orthorhombic sulfur and gaseous sulfur, taken from the SGTE91 reference and the gas-phase description in the database.

The formation enthalpies used are $\Delta fH^\circ = -168.6 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ (pyrite, FeS_2) and $-100.6 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ (pyrrhotite, FeS) from the Dilner–Mao–Selleby (2015) assessment, and $\Delta fH^\circ = -144.1 \pm 7.3 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ per $\text{FeS}_{1.33}$ for greigite (Subramani et al., 2020). Greigite is the only newly introduced phase and the only one carrying an experimentally determined uncertainty; the assessed pyrite and pyrrhotite enthalpies were held fixed. The $\pm 1\sigma$ (least-stable) bound shown on each diagram therefore reflects the greigite enthalpy uncertainty alone ($\pm 7.3 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ per $\text{FeS}_{1.33}$), obtained by shifting that enthalpy by $\pm 1\sigma$ and recomputing the boundaries.

3. Validation

Before adding stable greigite, two validation tests confirmed that the workflow reproduced the existing assessments. Treating greigite as metastable (excluding it from the phase set) recovered the classical $\text{Fe} \rightarrow \text{pyrrhotite} \rightarrow \text{pyrite}$ topology of the Dilner–Mao–Selleby assessment (Fig. 1). Excluding greigite in Fe–S–O reproduced the established topology in which magnetite is bounded by pyrrhotite and pyrite, including the magnetite–pyrite–hematite invariant point (Fig. 2).

This agreement shows that the database, the grand-potential formalism, and the workflow are implemented correctly. Because greigite is the only difference between the reproduced

classical diagrams and the revised ones, any topological change can be attributed directly to the updated greigite thermodynamics.

Figure 1. Validation 1: excluding greigite recovers the classical Fe → pyrrhotite → pyrite Fe–S diagram of the Dilner–Mao–Selleby assessment.

The boundary fugacities agreed with literature data (Tables 2 and 3). The greigite-excluded Fe–S boundaries reproduce the Dilner–Mao–Selleby assessment and are consistent with the experimental Toulmin–Barton (1964) pyrite–pyrrhotite curve (598–1016 K). The Fe–S–O oxide boundaries reproduce the standard buffers (Frost, 1991): the computed magnetite–hematite boundary, $\log f(\text{O}_2) = -68.2$ at 300 K, matched the buffer value $\log f(\text{O}_2) = -68.7$ ($4 \text{ Fe}_3\text{O}_4 + \text{O}_2 = 6 \text{ Fe}_2\text{O}_3$).

Table 2. Fe–S boundary sulfur fugacities, $\log f(\text{S}_2)$, at 300 K and 600 K (greigite excluded)

Boundary	$\log f(\text{S}_2)$ at 300 K	$\log f(\text{S}_2)$ 600 K	Literature / source
Fe / Fe_{1-x}S	-49.9	-21.6	Dilner–Mao–Selleby 2015 (reproduced)
Fe_{1-x}S / FeS_2	-31.8	-8.6	Dilner–Mao–Selleby 2015; Toulmin–Barton 1964 (exp., 598–1016 K; consistent at 600 K, extrapolated at 300

Figure 2. Validation 2: with greigite excluded, the workflow recovers the classical Fe–S–O topology at 300 K — magnetite borders both pyrrhotite and pyrite, with a magnetite/pyrite/hematite contact.

Table 3. Fe–S–O boundary fugacities at 300 K (greigite excluded)

Boundary	(log f) 300 K	Literature / source
Fe / Fe _{1-x} S (pyrrhotite)	log f(S ₂) = -49.3	Dilner–Mao–Selleby 2015 (reproduced)
Fe _{1-x} S / FeS ₂ (pyrite)	log f(S ₂) = -31.8	Dilner–Mao–Selleby 2015; Toulmin–Barton 1964 (exp.)
Fe / Fe ₃ O ₄ (magnetite)	log f(O ₂) = -87.4	iron–magnetite buffer (Frost 1991)
Fe ₃ O ₄ / Fe ₂ O ₃ (M–H buffer)	log f(O ₂) = -68.2	magnetite–hematite buffer (Frost 1991)
native-S saturation	log f(S ₂) = -13.8	vs solid orthorhombic S (2·GHSER_S); SGTE91

4. Results

4.1 Fe–S predominance diagram

Using the measured enthalpy of formation (Subramani et al., 2020) and heat capacity, the Fe–S diagram was recalculated from 300 to 600 K (Fig. 3). The pyrrhotite stability field was eliminated and replaced by an expanded greigite field as the stable sulfide intermediate between iron and pyrite; the boundary sulfur fugacities at 300 and 600 K are listed in Table 4. Adding greigite shifted the pyrite onset from $\log f(\text{S}_2) = -31.8$ to -20.3 at 300 K. The decomposition margin, the standard enthalpy of the reaction

is $+19.5 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. The positive value indicates that decomposition is endothermic and that greigite is stable with respect to pyrrhotite and pyrite. This agreed, within error, with the experimentally derived $+18.9 \pm 8.6 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ (Shumway et al., 2022) and the value computed directly from the database, $+21.5 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. Relative to the greigite enthalpy uncertainty alone ($\pm 7.3 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$), the margin was $+2.7\sigma$, so greigite is stable well within the experimental uncertainty; repeating the calculation with stoichiometric FeS gave $+21.1 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.

Figure 3. Fe–S stability diagram with greigite as a thermodynamically stable phase.

For comparison, the Fe–O predominance diagram (Fig. S4) showed a similar topology over 300–600 K. The Fe–O and Fe–S–O diagrams were computed from the same assembled database

(Dilner & Selleby, 2017, with the measured greigite line compound and pyrite on a common SGTE91 reference); no separate dataset was used.

The large uncertainty in the greigite enthalpy of formation ($\pm 7.3 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ per $\text{FeS}_{1.33}$; Subramani et al., 2020) propagates from the primary measured quantity, the drop-solution enthalpy ($-1071.6 \pm 6.2 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). Although that measurement error is small ($< 0.6 \%$), the formation enthalpy is a difference of large terms, so small absolute errors propagate into a significant uncertainty.

Propagating this uncertainty, an equilibrium pyrrhotite (Fe_{1-x}S) field existed only at the $+1\sigma$ (least-stable) bound of the greigite enthalpy (Fig. 4); the pyrrhotite field is therefore highly sensitive to the greigite uncertainty. This should not be read as evidence against pyrrhotite in nature, but it indicates that the equilibrium pyrrhotite field is much narrower than in the classical Fe–S diagrams. The greigite field and its $\pm 1\sigma$ margin are shown in Fig. 5, and the corresponding boundary fugacities are listed in Table 4.

Figure 4. Greigite stability field and its $\pm 1\sigma$ error margin. The central field (solid) is bracketed by $\pm 1\sigma$ bounds (dashed); the hatched band is the Fe_{1-x}S (pyrrhotite) field that appears only when greigite sits at its $+1\sigma$ (least-stable) bound.

Table 4. Fe–S boundary sulfur fugacities (in bars), $\log f(\text{S}_2)$, at 300 K and 600 K with greigite included with and without $+1\sigma$ (least stable) bound

Boundary	$\log f(\text{S}_2)$ at 300 K	$\log f(\text{S}_2)$ at 600 K
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	300 K	K
Fe / Fe ₃ S ₄	-50.7	-21.3
Fe / Fe _{1-x} S (+1σ)	-49.3	-21.3
Fe _{1-x} S / Fe ₃ S ₄ (+1σ)	-47.1	-17.7
Fe ₃ S ₄ / FeS ₂	-20.3	-2.7
Fe ₃ S ₄ / FeS ₂ (+1σ)	-24.1	-4.6

4.2 Fe–S–O predominance diagram

The Fe–S–O diagram at 300 K (Fig. 5A) was computed with the measured greigite enthalpy ($-144.1 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). Pyrrhotite had no equilibrium field; greigite occupied a large region and bordered the iron oxides directly. Consequently pyrite no longer shared a boundary with hematite and reached the oxide-dominated region only at the highest sulfur fugacities, where sulfates became stable. This topology is a thermodynamic consequence of the revised greigite stability, not a numerical or plotting artifact.

Wüstite (Fe_{1-x}O, the database HALITE phase) acquired a field at 300 K, but wüstite is well established to be metastable below its eutectoid ($\approx 833\text{--}843 \text{ K}$), where it disproportionates to iron and magnetite (Navrotsky et al., 2010); it was therefore excluded from the 300 K sections, consistent with its absence from low-temperature natural assemblages. The ferric-sulfate field at high oxygen fugacity is the equilibrium result of the assessment, and the full oxygen-fugacity range was retained for completeness.

Figure 5. **A.** Fe–S–O predominance diagram at 300 K. Greigite borders the iron oxides; pyrite borders the sulfates/native-S. **B.** Fe–S–O predominance diagram at 300 K with greigite at its +1 σ (least-stable) bound. A pyrrhotite field appears and pyrite borders hematite. Capped at native-S saturation.

When the greigite enthalpy was shifted to its +1 σ (least-stable) bound, the topology changed much as in the Fe–S diagram (Fig. 5B): a narrow equilibrium pyrrhotite field and the direct pyrite–hematite boundary of the classical Fe–S–O diagrams reappeared, confirming the strong sensitivity of the Fe–S–O topology to the greigite uncertainty.

At 600 K (Figs. 6A, B) the greigite field broadened toward sulfur saturation as the Fe/greigite and greigite/pyrite boundaries shifted to higher sulfur fugacity. The greigite/pyrite boundary lay at $\log f(\text{S}_2) = -2.7$, about 0.08 log units above the native-sulfur saturation limit ($\log f(\text{S}_2) = -2.78$), leaving no stability field for pyrite. At the +1 σ bound a narrow pyrrhotite field and the classical pyrite–oxide contact reappeared, as at 300 K.

The Fe–S–O boundary fugacities at 300 and 600 K (with and without the +1 σ bound) are listed in Table 5.

Figure 6 A. Fe–S–O predominance diagram at 600 K. The greigite field widens up the sulfur axis to the native-sulfur saturation limit and borders the iron oxides directly. Figure B. Fe–S–O predominance diagram at 600 K with greigite at its +1 σ (least-stable) bound. A narrow equilibrium pyrrhotite (Fe_{1-x}S) field reappears between iron and greigite, and pyrite re-emerges below the native-sulfur cap.

Table 5. Fe–S–O boundary fugacities (bars) at 300 and 600 K with greigite as a thermodynamically stable phase, with and without the +1 σ (least-stable) bound

Boundary	(log f) 300 K	(log f) 600 K	Literature / source
Fe / Fe ₃ O ₄	log f(O ₂) = -87.4	log f(O ₂) = -39.2	iron–magnetite buffer (Frost 1991); wüstite metastable at 300 and 600 K
Fe ₃ O ₄ / Fe ₂ O ₃	log f(O ₂) = -68.2	log f(O ₂) = -27.7	magnetite–hematite buffer (Frost 1991)
Fe / Fe ₃ S ₄	log f(S ₂) = -50.7	log f(S ₂) = -21.3	this work
Fe / Fe _{1-x} S +1 σ	log f(S ₂) = -49.3	log f(S ₂) = -21.3	this work
Fe _{1-x} S / Fe ₃ S ₄ +1 σ	log f(S ₂) = -47.1	log f(S ₂) = -17.7	this work
Fe ₃ S ₄ / FeS ₂	log f(S ₂) = -20.3	log f(S ₂) = -2.7	Toulmin–Barton 1964 (pyrite–pyrrhotite, exp.)
Fe ₃ S ₄ / FeS ₂ +1 σ	log f(S ₂) = -24.1	log f(S ₂) = -4.6	this work
native-S saturation	log f(S ₂) = -13.8	log f(S ₂) = -2.78	vs solid orthorhombic S (2·GHSER_S); SGTE91

4.3 Thermal stability of greigite

DSC with powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) of the products (Figs. S3, S4) constrained the thermal behavior of greigite between 300 and 873 K. Consistent with the DSC and in situ XRD of Chen et al. (2019), greigite remained stable to approximately 590 K, after which it began transforming to pyrite and pyrrhotite. Pyrite, pyrrhotite, and greigite then coexisted over a finite interval whose extent depends on the kinetics of sulfur redistribution. The equilibrium prediction and the observed multiphase coexistence are thus complementary: the former identifies the stable assemblage, the latter reflects the kinetic evolution of a closed system on heating.

DSC and PXRD were performed on the original sample synthesized and characterized by Subramani et al. (2020). The final product was dominated by pyrrhotite (Fe₇S₈) (Fig. S5), with possible trace magnetite. The thermal evolution (Fig. S4) was a complex sequence of overlapping

exothermic and endothermic processes beginning near 423 K. Some exothermic peaks likely reflect surface oxidation forming a thin oxide layer from trace oxygen or water in the nominally inert atmosphere; greigite's sensitivity to oxidation is well documented (Rickard et al., 2024). Letard et al. (2005) showed that natural greigite develops an amorphous iron-oxide shell around a crystalline core, and Chen et al. (2026) report that low-temperature oxidation commonly produces greigite-core/magnetite-shell structures. The large endothermic event near 700 K marked transformation of the sulfide assemblage to a high-temperature, likely metastable pyrrhotite; Chen et al. (2019) similarly report progressive transformation in which pyrite and pyrrhotite form while greigite persists, followed by pyrite–pyrrhotite coexistence and finally pyrrhotite alone. On cooling, a sharp exothermic peak near 573 K (Fig. S4) suggested a reversible transformation of the high-temperature phase to the pyrrhotite seen in Fig. S5.

Repeated DSC and PXRD on an original Subramani et al. (2020) sample stored for about six years (Figs. S6, S7) gave a thermal profile similar to the original, though the transformations between 423 and 700 K are more clearly separated. The main endothermic decomposition occurred at essentially the same temperature in both runs, indicating an unchanged transformation pathway. The aged product contained about 10–15 wt% magnetite, whereas in the original experiment the magnetite was near the PXRD detection limit (< 1 wt%) — consistent with growth of an iron-oxide shell around a greigite core with time and air exposure (Letard et al., 2005; Chen et al., 2026).

5. Discussion

The revised greigite thermodynamics suggests a parallel with the Fe–O system. Magnetite (Fe_3O_4) and greigite (Fe_3S_4) have inverse spinel structure with mixed Fe(II,III) oxidation state. In the classical Fe–O system, magnetite forms a broad stability field between metallic iron and hematite, while wüstite (Fe_{1-x}O) is stable at higher temperatures and more reducing conditions. Similarly, in the Fe–S system, greigite occupies an intermediate position between pyrrhotite and pyrite. The recalculated phase stability diagrams indicates that incorporating greigite as a stable phase and significantly modifies the classical Fe–S topology. In the present assessment the pyrrhotite stability field is reduced and exists only within the experimental uncertainty of the greigite thermodynamic measurements. It should be noted that pyrrhotite remains a common natural phase and is observed during thermal transformation of greigite, whereas wüstite is largely absent from low-temperature geological environments. Nevertheless, the results imply that greigite may play a significantly larger role in low temperature Fe–S phase equilibria than has traditionally been assumed analogous to the magnetite in the Fe–O phases.

The strong sensitivity of the pyrrhotite–greigite boundary to small changes in thermodynamic parameters places pyrrhotite at a marginal position in the low-temperature Fe–S system. Quantitatively, an equilibrium pyrrhotite field appears only when the greigite enthalpy of formation is shifted by its full $+1\sigma$ ($\approx +7$ kJ·mol⁻¹ per $\text{FeS}_{1.33}$). The widespread occurrence of pyrrhotite in low-temperature sediments may therefore reflect non-equilibrium pathways, incomplete equilibration, or local variations in sulfur fugacity and redox near the greigite–pyrrhotite boundary rather than a broad equilibrium field. The DSC studies support this

interpretation by demonstrating that pyrrhotite readily forms during greigite transformation and can coexist with greigite and pyrite over a finite temperature interval. The broad equilibrium stability field predicted for greigite between 300 and 600 K and over a wide range of sulfur fugacity supports its occurrence under a broader range of diagenetic conditions than would be expected for a strictly metastable phase.

Including greigite as a thermodynamically stable phase similarly results in a modification of the Fe–S–O system. In the classical Fe–O–S stability diagrams of Holland (1959), magnetite occupies the intermediate stability field between metallic iron and hematite and wüstite is restricted to high temperatures and more reducing conditions. The sulfide side of the diagram is defined by pyrrhotite and pyrite, with the pyrrhotite–magnetite boundary terminating at a pyrite–pyrrhotite–magnetite invariant point. The sulfide–oxide boundary then continues as a pyrite–magnetite coexistence line that intersects the magnetite–hematite boundary at a pyrite–magnetite–hematite invariant point. Thus pyrite maintains direct equilibrium relationships with both magnetite and hematite in the classical topology.

At 300 K when the experimental enthalpy of formation of greigite is used for the calculations, it occupies a substantial portion of the Fe–S–O stability field and directly borders both magnetite and hematite. As a result, the classical pyrite–hematite contact disappears and pyrite reaches the oxide-dominated region only at the highest sulfur fugacities. At 600 K, the relative stability of greigite, pyrrhotite, and pyrite changes, and the extent of the greigite stability field decreases relative to 300 K. The resulting topology differs substantially from the classical Fe–S–O sections of Holland (1959). In the classical system, increasing temperature progressively compresses the pyrite stability field toward the sulfur-saturation boundary, leaving only a narrow pyrite region at high temperature. In the present assessment, the thermodynamically stable greigite occupies much of the intermediate sulfide stability region and shifts the greigite–pyrite boundary to higher sulfur fugacity. Consequently, the pyrite stability field lies entirely within the native sulfur field and is eliminated from the accessible Fe–S–O topology. Stable greigite produces 600 K Fe–S–O topology, which resembles the high temperature compression of the pyrite field observed in the classical system, but the effect is larger.

In both cases, when the greigite enthalpy is shifted to its $+1\sigma$ (least stable) bound, both pyrrhotite and pyrite stability fields reappear. The resulting topology suggests that greigite may play a larger role in Fe–S–O equilibria at low temperatures acting as a thermodynamically important intermediate phase that controls large portions of the stability field.

The thermal behavior shows that greigite does not transform in a single step: greigite, pyrite, and pyrrhotite coexist over a finite interval (this work; Chen et al., 2019), reflecting kinetics rather than equilibrium. The aging experiment suggests that the long term preservation of greigite in sediments may not require complete protection from oxidation since the formation of an iron oxide shell encapsulating the greigite core can limit the direct exposure of the sulfide phase to oxidizing conditions. Moreover, despite the development of approximately 10–15 wt% magnetite during six years of aging, the overall thermal profile and the main decomposition event remain similar indicating that the oxide shell does not change the transformation mechanisms. Together with the revised thermodynamic data, these observations suggest that the widespread

occurrence of natural greigite may be due to not only its thermodynamic stability, but also to the development of a protective oxide surface layer.

6. Conclusions

An open, reproducible CALPHAD workflow was used to reassess the Fe–S and Fe–S–O predominance diagrams with greigite as a thermodynamically stable phase. Suppressing greigite recovers the classical assessments and the standard buffers, validating the approach. Including thermodynamically stable greigite substantially modifies both systems. In Fe–S, greigite occupies the intermediate Fe(II,III) position between iron and pyrite and reduces the equilibrium pyrrhotite field, which reappears only within the greigite enthalpy uncertainty. In Fe–S–O, greigite borders magnetite and hematite, eliminating the classical pyrite–hematite contact at 300 K. Thermal analysis and PXRD show that greigite remains stable to approximately 600 K before transforming through a sequence of overlapping processes to a high temperature pyrrhotite phase. The thermodynamic calculations and the experimental observations suggest a narrow stability field for the pyrrhotite within the low temperature Fe–S system and that its occurrence may reflect not only equilibrium stability but also non-equilibrium kinetic controls on mineral transformation pathways. Additionally, the results demonstrate the importance of reproducible computational frameworks for reassessing long-established geochemical phase diagrams.

Data Availability

Name: greigite-fes-tdb (a reproducible greigite Fe–S(–O) CALPHAD workflow developed by Odinzen LLC, built on pycalphad). Developers: the authors (Odinzen LLC). Year first available: 2026. Language: Python 3 (pycalphad 0.11.1, NumPy, SciPy, Matplotlib). License: source code under the MIT License (OSI-approved). Code, thermodynamic databases (.tdb), and figure-generation scripts will be archived on GitHub and Zenodo, with databases and extracted data under CC-BY 4.0. The reproduction package — source code, thermodynamic databases (.tdb), and figure-generation scripts — is openly available on GitHub at <https://github.com/odinzen/greigite-fes-tdb> and archived on Zenodo at [https://doi.org/\[Zenodo DOI to be inserted on submission\]](https://doi.org/[Zenodo DOI to be inserted on submission]).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Michael Bustamante: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. Gabriel Bustamante: Software, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. Tamilarasan Subramani: Investigation (DSC and PXRD measurements), Writing – review & editing. Kristina Lilova: Data analysis and interpretation, Validation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. Alexandra Navrotsky: Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

M. Bustamante and G. Bustamante are affiliated with Odinzen LLC, a company developing computational-thermodynamics tools; this affiliation is disclosed. The authors declare no other competing financial or personal interests.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies

During the preparation of this work the authors used Claude (Opus, developed by Anthropic) and Gemini (developed by Google), AI assistants, to help build the open-source, reproducible CALPHAD workflow (thermodynamic-database retrieval, knowledge-graph extraction of calorimetric data, deterministic TDB construction, and grand-potential predominance-diagram computation), to generate and refine the figures from the underlying data and workflow output, and to assist with drafting and editing the manuscript. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Appendix A. Supplementary Material

Supplementary material associated with this article comprises the experimental methods (greigite synthesis and characterization, differential scanning calorimetry, and powder X-ray diffraction) and supplementary figures, including the reproducible computational workflow, the greigite heat-capacity Debye–Einstein fit, the Fe–O predominance diagram, and the differential scanning calorimetry and powder X-ray diffraction of the original (2020) and aged (2026) greigite samples.

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